

MULTI-SCALE MODELLING OF FIBRE BUNDLES

N. D. Chakladar¹, P. Mandal^{1*}, P. Potluri²

¹ School of Mechanical, Aerospace and Civil Engineering, The University of Manchester, UK

² North-West Composites Centre, The University of Manchester, UK

* Corresponding author (p.mandal@manchester.ac.uk)

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1 Introduction

Continuous fibre reinforced composites undergo a number of different manufacturing processes. Most of these processes guide the composite part properties and quality. Being a two-phase component for the embedding matrix and reinforcing fibre, interactions are inevitable both at fibre and tow level. Hence, the authors tried to look into those interactions at intra- and inter-tow level without the matrix – the dry fibre mechanics of the assembly. Moreover, in case of woven fabric some inevitable physical phenomena are fibre migration and fibre entanglement which play a vital role in the deformation of the structure affecting the part mechanical properties. These phenomena mostly take place before resin infusion and thus understanding such dry fibre mechanics is a priority for deformation and structural integrity of the manufactured part. These investigations under experimental regime will become a heavy expense, thus, paving the way for the numerical models to get through. Nevertheless, the computational expense also reaches its crux while accounting a number of tows in a fabric; each tow consisting of about thousands of filaments. Hence, the modeling of deformation of fibres (micro-scale), tows (meso) and the fabric (macro) under load cannot be dealt with ease at every detail because of these issues. Multi-scale mechanics, a recent promising approach in numerical methods entices the researchers from various fields to address such research-loopholes or limits in a better manner without jeopardizing the accuracy. So, it was not an exception in this case. The authors of this paper focused on the multi-scale modeling of fibre bundles with a view to improve the numerical modeling technique for better computational efficiency and fruitfully address the deformation mechanics at inter- and intra-tow level. The main objective of this study was to develop

numerical models at different scales so that it can account the intra-tow deformations with less computational effort and realistic assumptions. The following sections detail the modeling strategy at fibre and bundle level and how the present model simplifies the traditional 3D continuum approach and the beam segment approach.

2 Present methodology

2.1 Past studies

Researchers [1-2] considered continuum models for assembly of fibres, but the fibre count was upto 100 for massive computational time and effort. Digital element simulation also showed a profound contribution in this field but was also restricted to fibre count. The present research conducted some initial studies on fibre assemblies' up to 63 fibres carrying out simple bending analysis, yet, cost computational efficiency. Thus, multi-scale modeling in 3D for fibre bundle didn't come out cost effective. At this point, it was conceptualized to idealize the 3D deformation of fibre bundles into 2D analyses while including the deformation information due to transverse loading into the 2D model which significantly improved the computational power. The methodology of this new analysis has been discussed in the next section.

2.2 Methodology

2.2.1 Experimental study

A typical T700SC-12000-50C Toray carbon tow consists of about 12k filaments with an average diameter of 7 μ . In T700SC; T700S denotes a tensile strength of 711 ksi or 4.9 GPa and C denotes the fibres were never twisted, 12000 is the tow size. 50C denotes the sizing features – where 5 represents the system compatibility for general purpose epoxy,

phenolic, poly ester or vinyl ester resins, 0 denotes that surface is treated for better adhesion with resins. C denotes the amount of sizing added to the fibres for better handling and weaving (= 1.0% of the sizing material). The properties of the material are acquired from manufacturer's datasheet and literature.

Compaction tests were carried out on such tows investigating the effects of different parameters – load (10-50cN in steps of 10cN), twist (0.26, 0.32, 0.38, 0.43, 0.49, 0.55 turns/cm), tow size (1.5k, 3k, 6k, 12k). The specimen effective length is 34.5 cm. A yarn compaction tester (Fig 1.) was used for the purpose that interfaced with LabVIEW to register the load corresponding to displacement of the probe [ref]. The tester consisted of three distinct regions – probe slider/anvil which was a displacement based control, sample mouting with one end screwed to a micrometer (to apply twist) and other end attached to a suspended dead load (for prestressing the twisted tow), and a bottom camera to capture the lateral spreading of the tow. For the sake of simplicity the present article has focused on modeling an untwisted tow of 12k fibre filaments prestressed with a 50cN load with an initial assumption of ideal distribution of voids throughout the fibre assembly. The load-displacement plots obtained from the experiment are used to compare with the numerical model.

Fig 1. Yarn compaction tester

2.2.2 Numerical modeling

The multi-scale model was developed using a commercial FE package called Abaqus. The numerical model for a 12k tow was developed in different scales because of computational intensity

and effort. Initial 3D models of 30 fibre assembly was built in and meshed with 2240 solid elements per fibre. Boundary conditions were specified in the form of tension of 0.04 cN load (calculated based on 50cN for 12k tow) applied to an end of the filaments which is simply supported and the other end fixed. Two rigid platens were considered with the bottom one fixed and the top moving downwards with a constant velocity of 0.004 mm/s (same as the anvil downward speed in the experiment). The analysis was displacement-based and quasi-static. The material properties for the computation were obtained from literature and manufacturer's T700 datasheet. The simulation was found to increase the computational cost at a high extent in a quad-core processor and 48 GB RAM and was not found worthy enough to proceed with 3D multiscale. This led the authors to explore the multiscale analysis with incorporating the longitudinal behavior (in this case, the bending stiffness of the filaments) into 2D models assuming maximum compaction at the mid-cross sectional plane of the specimen.

The bending of a filament due to transverse loading can be assumed to take place in both perpendicular longitudinal planes. This bending stiffness is analytically estimated for a filament pre-stressed with a defined load. This bending stiffness information is then included in a beam column formulation to get the loading stiffness which, in turn, used as stiffness for springs attached to each fibre cross-sections at the centroid. Eq(1) shows the calculation of spring stiffness (k) based on beam column formula; where E represent fibre longitudinal modulus, I the second moment of inertia, L the effective length of the beam (fibre filament in this case), P the applied load at the end and P_{cr} the critical load to buckle.

$$k = \frac{48EI}{L^3} \left(1 + \frac{P}{P_{cr}} \right) \quad \text{Eq.(1)}$$

Fig 2. shows the diagram of simply supported beam pre-stressed (right) and a single fibre cross-section is attached to two springs (horizontal and vertical) which are grounded.

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Fig. 2. 2D section of a fibre filament with springs representing the bending stiffness

A two stage model was developed – one with a circular assembly of 127 filaments, and other an array of 94 bundles (each bundle consisted of 127 filaments) totaling to approx 12k filaments.

Fibre level modeling

The main assumptions for fibre level model were as follows: a) The bending stiffness was considered at the middle plane of cross-section along the length i.e. area under maximum compression, b) The total void fraction (in this case, 31%) was preserved from fibre (~20%) to bundle level (~10%), c) Uniform distribution of void and fibres in a circular arrangement, d) Cross-sections were assumed as plane strain and transversely isotropic. e) Fibre migration, breakage and entanglement were not considered in the present study, f) Fibres were untwisted and straight.

The fibre-level model consisted of 127 filaments evenly scattered and each filament was attached to springs both horizontally and vertically in the plane of cross-section. The fibres were meshed with 112 quadrilateral linear elements with characteristic dimension of the element length as $1/20^{\text{th}}$ of the diameter of a fibre. The loading rate, being 0.004mm/s, the analysis was taken as a quasi-static process. The interactions was defined as penalty contact and the authors have separately carried out investigation on friction of carbon tow at different angles and tow size which yielded a coefficient of friction of 0.4 when the tows are parallel. This information was useful to model the interaction between the fibres. The friction law used here is coulombian type. **Fig 3a** shows the 127 fibre-assembly before compaction and **Fig 3b** after compaction.

Fig. 3. 127 fibre-assembly a) before compaction, and b) after compaction

The reaction at the fixed boundary represented the actual load of compression which was then plotted against displacement of the top platen. This plot shows a gradual rise in the load with a lower stiffness as the effective void fraction reduced with each increment and then became steep when most of the fibres were in contact and the normal pressure at the contact points contributed more to the reaction load. This second slope was more responsible for the compression modulus of the bundle when it reached minimum void fraction. **Fig. 4** shows the non-linear load displacement curve for a 127 fibre-assembly.

Fig. 4. Load-displacement response for 127 fibre assembly under compaction

Bundle level modeling

The next stage of modeling was at bundle level with an assembly of 94 bundles. Since, the cross-section of the carbon tow was rectangular, this arrangement was made in a rectangular array. The underlying assumptions in this level of analysis were as follows: a) The spring stiffnesses were again considered at the mid plane of maximum compression, b) The bundle sections were plain strain and transversely isotropic, c) Material information was carried forward from the fibre level to the bundle where each bundle was a homogenous continuum from a discrete fibre-assembly, d) The void fraction was preserved and the outer diameter of the bundle assembly was equal to the average yarn diameter. Special attention was given to the evaluation of the properties of a homogenous bundle from a 127 fibre-assembly. This stage was the **discrete-to-continua** conversion based on equivalence of loading response. A 2D plane strain model was developed with a single bundle of diameter (92.32μ) equivalent to that of 127 fibre-assembly and numerical analysis was carried out on the compaction of such a bundle. The model was meshed with 182 quadrilateral linear elements. It was assumed that the density of the bundle will be equivalent to the fibres at all the stage. Now, the two required parameters for this analysis were the stress-strain relation and the poisson's ratio. As it can be observed from **Fig 4** the stress-strain behavior was hyper-elastic. The stress due to transverse loading was obtained from the S22 variable as the loading was in 2-direction (Fibre longitudinal – 1 direction and in-plane – 2-3 directions). The hyper-elastic

material models are, in general, provided with strain energy potentials that define the stored strain energy in the material per unit volume as a function of strain at that point of the material. The hyper-elastic model is then simplified into multi-linear elastic material model with increasing stiffness with strain. The load-displacement plot for 127 fibre-assembly was compared with the equivalent homogenous bundle and a poisson's ratio of 0.4 was found to match well with the fibre level compaction. The analysis was then carried forward with 94 such bundles and compaction with a rigid platen from the top moving downward with a velocity of 0.004 mm/s. This final assembly of 94 bundles has a thickness of 0.57 mm and span of 1.3 mm where all the bundles were ideally spaced. Each of 94 bundles was meshed with 182 quadrilateral linear elements. **Fig 5** shows how the material model has been linearized into two slopes. The nominal strain obtained from the MATLAB code was then modified accordingly to true (logarithmic) strain so that it can be implement in the ABAQUS material model through a user subroutine coded in FORTRAN.

Fig 5. Tri-linearization of material model for the bundle level

A subroutine UMAT was written that took care of the elastic modulus for two different strain ranges and was incorporated in ABAQUS input file. The rectangular arrangement of 94 bundles has been shown in the **Fig 6 (a)** before compaction and **Fig 6 (b)** after compaction.

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Fig 6. 94 bundle assembly (a) before and (b) after compaction

2.3 Results and discussion

The load displacement plots were obtained from 94 bundle assembly and compared with the 127 fibre model and with experiments. All these plots were needed to be normalized as reaction load per filament to a normalized displacement of the anvil. These resulted in a promising comparison, yet, as twist was not included in the model so the higher values of experimental response were not met (**Fig. 7**)

Fig. 7. Comparison of load-displacement between fibre level and bundle level with experiments

At the fibre level further numerical analyses were carried out on higher bundle sizes to capture the size effect on the load-displacement response. The ideal distribution of fibres assumed in the numerical analysis reflects the intra-tow fibre distribution as coming out of the spinneret during tow manufacturing. This tow is then stretched and wound around the bobbins at different stages and further compaction is carried out at the composite processing techniques. All these steps of intermittent compaction of the tow were captured in the following numerical model thus justifies its versatility.

2.4 Conclusion

The present numerical model shows a novel approach of predicting the deformation of yarns (here called as tows) with a multi-scale approach – that has significantly improved the computational power. Similar studies have been done for 3D straight fibre filaments meshed with beam elements which are to be compared with the realistic tow deformation behavior. A Matlab script is written that generates the Abaqus input file for user-defined number of filaments. Further studies are yet to be conducted on twisted tows with fibre migration taken into account and the node/element information thus generated can then be incorporated into the Matlab file. Thus the predictability of tow deformation at various stages of compaction in the composites manufacturing and processing techniques were addressed in this research.

3.3 References

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